

FAILURE ANALYSIS OF NOTCHED FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Due to their advantages such as high specific modulus and high specific strength, advanced fiber-reinforced composite materials are being widely used in fields like aerospace, weapons and marine, etc. In most of the numerical models, fiber-reinforced composites are modeled as homogeneous anisotropic plates and no special treatments are taken for the stress concentration at the notch tip. Such models cannot describe the stress states in the composites accurately. This article presents a detailed analysis on stress concentration in notched fiber-reinforced composites. Due to the formation of longitudinal splitting at notch tips along the fiber direction, the extremely high stress concentrations ahead of the notch tips could be drastically reduced for composites under remote tension. An efficient finite element model is created in this article in order to better understand the failure mechanisms of notched composite laminates. To capture the true stress concentration at the notch tip, in-ply surface-based cohesive contact along fiber direction were introduced in the finite element model to simulate the splitting. To modeling the delamination, interface cohesive contacts were introduced between plies. Failure modes and failure loads obtained from finite element analyses were compared with experimental results to confirm the failure mechanisms of composite laminates.

1 INTRODUCTION

Since the early 1960s, when advanced fiber-reinforced composites were first used in aerospace structures and sports equipments, the vast potential of fibrous composite materials has been seriously exploited by engineers and scientists [1]. The initial development and application of advanced fibrous composites were pursued primarily because of their potentials for lighter structures and improved performance. Today fibrous composites are usually the choice of designers for a variety of reasons, including low density, high stiffness, high strength, low thermal expansion, corrosion resistance, long fatigue life, adaptability to the intended function of the structure, and so on [2]. Because of these unique advantages, we are now on the verge of an explosion in the use of fibrous composite materials. Recently people can see their wide application in aircraft, marine, automotive structures, biomedical products, etc.

Unlike monolithic materials, fibrous composite materials are composed of two or more different phases and may develop multiple failure modes. These failure modes include fiber breakage, fiber pullout, fiber kinking, fiber/matrix debonding, matrix cracking at the fiber/matrix level, and delamination at the laminate level, all of which may have strong interactions with one another. These failure modes result in a loss in stiffness and strength of the composite materials, and sometimes may lead to catastrophic disasters. Therefore, there is an urgent need for efficient models to predict the damage propagation and ultimate strength of composite materials.

Over the past decades, many attempts have been made to investigate the strength and failure mechanisms of composite laminates. One of them is based on the concept of linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) carried over directly from homogeneous isotropic materials [3-4]. This approach assumes that failure occurs if the notch in a composite laminate, represented by an equivalent crack,

reaches a critical size. The strength of the laminate is related to the fracture toughness or the strain energy release rate. These two material parameters can be determined by testing cracked laminates. A second approach is based on the elastic stress distribution in the vicinity of the notch in an anisotropic composite plate. Failure strength was estimated by using some simplified stress fracture criteria, among which the point stress criterion and average stress criterion proposed by Whitney and Nuismer [5] are the two most popular ones. The point stress criterion assumes that failure occurs when the stress at a characteristic distance from the notch boundary attains the strength of unnotched material, whereas the average stress criterion predicts failure when the average stress over a characteristic distance from the notch boundary reaches the strength of unnotched material. The characteristic distance in these two criteria are determined by testing notched laminates. Although the point and average stress criteria provide reasonable solutions for some preliminary sizing design, the characteristic distance is not a material property and has no any physical meaning. It varies with the material type, lay-up and geometry of specimen [6].

For the above LEFM- and stress-based approaches, the stress distribution in composite laminates is typically calculated based on the anisotropic elasticity with the original notch geometry, and no damage evolution is considered. In most cases, however, complete failure is preceded by some subcritical damage. The subcritical damage may substantially alter the stress distribution, especially near the notch-tip of the composite laminates. Therefore, it is important to take into account the stress redistribution caused by damage progression prior to complete failure. In order to predict the failure strength more accurately, extensive research has been devoted to progressive failure analysis of notched composites by using the material property degradation method (MPDM). This method assumes that the damaged material can be replaced by an equivalent material with degraded stiffness properties. Once damage is detected in a composite material based on a chosen failure theory, the elastic moduli of the material are modified according to the failure modes. The material property degradation method can be applied either to one whole ply [7-8] (referred to as ply-discount method) or to finite elements [9-10]. So far most of the progressive failure analyses of notched composites are still based on the homogenization assumption, which treated composites as homogenized anisotropic materials. It has been shown by Liu and Tang [11] that this assumption introduces very severe stress concentrations at notch tips and makes the finite element calculation mesh-dependent. However, real composite materials have fibre and matrix constituents, and longitudinal splitting in terms of matrix cracking may emanate from notch tips along the fiber direction [12-13]. The formation of the splitting blunts the notches and reduces the stress concentrations correspondingly. Unfortunately, the material property degradation method may fail to model the splitting and the consequent fiber stress relaxation [11, 14]. Recently, Wisnom and co-workers [15-18] carried out a systematic analysis for damage progression in notched composite laminates by considering both the intra-ply splitting and the inter-ply delamination. The simulation results compare very well with the experimental observations.

In the present paper, we shall focus mostly on the progressive failure analysis of a double notched quasi-isotropic composite laminate under remote tension. The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the approach of modeling longitudinal splitting in each ply by surface-based cohesive behavior. In Section 3, damage progression in the double-notched tensile laminate is studied by considering both intra- and inter-ply damage modes. Some concluding remarks are given in Section 4.

2 LONGITUDINAL SPLITTING AND DELAMINATION MODELLING BY SURFACE-BASED COHESIVE CONTACT

Cohesive elements are frequently used at interfaces between individual plies of composite laminates to predict delamination [19-20], and seldom used to predict intra-ply splitting [11, 16-18]. One drawback of the cohesive element method is that it requires the same mesh seeds for the two surfaces between which cohesive elements are inserted to model the delamination or splitting. This necessarily means that the method may not be applicable to composites with general lay-ups because the splitting lines vary with fiber orientations of the plies and it is hard to create a finite element mesh with the same configuration for all plies [11]. To overcome this drawback, the surface-based cohesive contact method is adopted in this paper to model the inter-ply delamination and intra-ply splitting. Similar to the cohesive element method, the surface-based cohesive contact method also combines a

strength-based analysis to predict the damage initiation, and a fracture mechanics analysis to predict the crack propagation. However, cohesive traction-separation behavior is defined between the two surfaces where delamination or splitting is supposed to occur, and no cohesive element is needed. The surface-based cohesive behavior assumes a linear traction-separation law prior to damage,

$$\begin{pmatrix} t_n \\ t_s \\ t_t \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} k_n^0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & k_s^0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & k_t^0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \delta_n \\ \delta_s \\ \delta_t \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where t_n , t_s and t_t are the one normal and two tangential traction components, δ_n , δ_s and δ_t are the corresponding separations. The stiffness components in Equation (1) can be calculated based on the elastic moduli of the material and the assumed thickness of the interface [11].

Damage initiates if a strength-based quadratic criterion is satisfied,

$$\left(\frac{\langle t_n \rangle}{N} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{t_s}{S} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{t_t}{T} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

where N , S and T are the one normal and two tangential cohesive strengths, $\langle \rangle$ represents the Macaulay bracket of value zero when its argument is negative.

Damage propagation is governed by fracture energy. The dependence of the fracture energy on the mode mix is defined based on criterion

$$\left(\frac{G_n}{G_n^C} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{G_s}{G_s^C} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{G_t}{G_t^C} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (3)$$

with the mixed-mode fracture energy $G^C = G_n + G_s + G_t$ when the above condition is satisfied. In this expression, quantities G_n , G_s and G_t refer to the work done by the tractions and their conjugate relative separations in the normal and shear directions, respectively. Quantities with superscript C denote the critical strain energy release rates corresponding to each fracture mode.

After damage initiation, the damage evolution is characterized by progressive degradation of the cohesive stiffness. A scalar damage variable D representing the state of damage at the contact point is defined. It is assigned a value of 0 for undamaged states, monotonically increases upon further loading after damage initiation, and acquires a value of 1 for complete failure. The post-initiation traction versus separation relation is of the form

$$\begin{aligned} t_n &= \begin{cases} (1-D)k_n^0 \delta_n & \delta_n > 0 \\ k_n^0 \delta_n & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ t_s &= (1-D)k_s^0 \delta_s \\ t_t &= (1-D)k_t^0 \delta_t \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The evolution law for D is based upon the assumption that the tractions decrease linearly with increasing separation once damage has initiated,

$$D = \frac{\frac{2G^C}{t_e^0} (\delta_e^{\max} - \delta_e^0)}{\delta_e^{\max} \left(\frac{2G^C}{t_e^0} - \delta_e^0 \right)} \quad (5)$$

where δ_e^{\max} is the maximum effective separation attained during the loading history, while δ_e^0 and t_e^0 are the effective separation and effective traction at damage initiation. The effective separation and work-conjugate effective traction are defined by

$$\delta_e = \sqrt{\langle \delta_n \rangle^2 + \delta_s^2 + \delta_t^2} \quad (6)$$

and

$$t_e = \sqrt{\langle t_n \rangle^2 + t_s^2 + t_t^2} \quad (7)$$

respectively.

3 FAILURE ANALYSIS OF DOUBLE-NOTCHED COMPOSITE LAMINATE

Hallett and Wisnom [15] has performed a series of experiments on double-notched E-glass/913 composite laminates under remote tension. In this paper, a quasi-isotropic laminate with lay-up of $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ and width of 20mm is modelled and compared with the experiments. Fig. 1 shows the geometry of the specimen. The notch angle (θ) in the test was 60° . However, no difference was observed between a sharp notch and an angled notch since the subcritical damage modifies the stress field once the splitting initiates [15]. To accommodate the notch and the potential splitting routes for $\pm 45^\circ$ plies, a notch angle of $\theta=90^\circ$ is used in the finite element analysis. Experimental results show damage initiation from the notch tip in the form of matrix cracking and longitudinal splitting within each ply. With the applied load increasing, delamination near the notch tip develops. At the maximum load, fiber fracture quickly grows across the width of specimen. In this section, a progressive failure analysis is carried out for this double-notched laminate with the surface-based cohesive contact method described in Section 2. The material properties of the composite system follow those of Hallett and Wisnom [15-16] and are given in Table 1.

Figure 1: Geometry of the double-notched laminate

Due to the symmetry of the problem in thickness direction, only one half of the laminate is modelled by using the commercial software Abaqus/Explicit. Each ply is modelled with one 3D continuum element (C3D8R in Abaqus notation) in the thickness direction. The Hashin failure criterion [21] is coded in a VUMAT user-subroutine to predict matrix cracking and fiber failure. To predict the initiation and propagation of the longitudinal splitting in the $\pm 45^\circ$ and 0° plies, surface-based cohesive contact behaviour is specified between two adjacent surfaces along the green lines in Fig. 2 which emanate from the notch tip and extend to the free edge along the fiber direction. This makes the in-plane meshes are different for different plies. For delamination prediction, surface-based cohesive contact behaviour is specified between any two adjacent plies. The traction-separation laws for delamination and longitudinal splitting are assumed to be the same, as described in Section 2.

Modulus in fiber direction E_1 (GPa)	43.9
Transverse moduli $E_2=E_3$ (GPa)	15.4

Shear moduli $G_{12}=G_{13}$ (GPa)	4.34
Shear modulus G_{23} (GPa)	3.5
Poisson's ratios $\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	0.3
Poisson's ratio ν_{23}	0.5
Tensile strength in fiber direction X (MPa)	1540
Compressive strength in fiber direction X' (MPa)	620
Transverse tensile strengths $Y=Z$ (MPa)	39
Transverse compressive strengths $Y'=Z'$ (MPa)	128
Shear strengths $S_{12}=S_{13}$ (MPa)	89
Shear strength S_{23} (MPa)	89

Table1: Material properties of E-glass/913 composite used in FE model [15-16]

Figure 2: Finite element meshes for the notch tip area of each ply of the double-notched laminate.

The maximum applied far field stresses at failure is predicted to be 163MPa, and the error is about 20% of the mean test ultimate strength (204MPa). Analogous to the damage progression observed in experiments, finite element simulation reveals that damage initiates at the notch tip in the form of matrix cracking in the 90° ply and longitudinal splitting in other three plies. On continuation of loading, the matrix cracking diffuses in the central section and the longitudinal splitting propagates, and meanwhile delamination develops in a narrow area along the splitting. Ultimate failure occurs with fiber fracture at the notch tip in the 0° ply and it progresses rapidly across the width of the laminate. For convenience and ease of comparison with the tested specimen, damage modes including matrix cracking, longitudinal splitting, fiber fracture and delamination at 100% of the maximum load are superimposed to form a composite damage map as shown in Fig. 3a. The uniformly distributed black lines represent the predicted matrix cracking in each ply. Although each damaged element may contain a great number of microcracks, only one dominant matrix crack is drawn for each element. The green lines represent the predicted longitudinal splitting, the red line represents the fiber fracture in the 0° ply, and the shaded areas denote the delamination. In comparison with the observed damage from experiments in Fig. 3b, most of the features of damage are replicated. However, the fiber failure in the 90° ply observed in the tests is not predicted. The fiber failure in the 90° ply is probably due to the

shearing induced by the adjacent $+45^\circ$ and -45° plies, so some parametric studies on fiber shearing strength and interlaminar shear properties should be performed further.

Figure 3: Comparison of predicted damage pattern with experimental result at the maximum load of the double-notched laminate.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A finite element model is developed to perform the progressive failure analysis of a double-notched quasi-isotropic composite laminate in tension. The surfaced-based cohesive contact method is used to predict the intra-ply longitudinal splitting and inter-ply delamination. In such a way, general composite laminates with any stacking sequence can be modelled through a biased finite element mesh. The model gives an accurate description of the main damage features, including the longitudinal splitting, extensive matrix cracking and also the delamination area. A good correlation of finite element simulation to experimental results in open literature is achieved.

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REFERENCES

- [1] C.T. Herakovich, On the relationship between engineering properties and delamination of composite materials, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **15**, 1981, pp. 336-348.
- [2] I.M. Daniel and O. Ishai, Engineering mechanics of composite materials, 2nd ed., Oxford University Press, New York. 2006.
- [3] M.E. Waddoups, J.R. Eisenmann and B.E. Kaminski, Macroscopic fracture mechanisms of advanced composite materials, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **5**, 1971, pp. 446-454.
- [4] I. Eriksson and C.G. Aronsson, Strength of tensile loaded graphite/epoxy laminates containing cracks, open and filled holes, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **24**, 1990, pp. 456-482.
- [5] J.M. Whitney and R.J. Nuismer, Stress fracture criteria for laminated composites containing stress concentrations, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **8**, 1974, pp. 253-265.
- [6] P.P. Camanho and M. Lambert, A design methodology for mechanically fastened joints in laminated composite materials, *Composite Science and Technology*, **66**, 2006, pp. 3004-3020.
- [7] B.G. Prusty, Progressive failure analysis of laminated unstiffened and stiffened composite panels, *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, **24**, 2005, pp. 633-642.

- [8] P. Pal and C. Ray, Progressive failure analysis of laminated composite plates by finite element method, *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, **21**, 2002, pp. 1505-1513.
- [9] S.C. Tan and J. Perez, Progressive failure of laminated composites with a hole under compressive loading, *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, **12**, 1993, pp. 1043-1057.
- [10] P.P. Camanho and F.L. Matthews, A progressive damage model for mechanically fastened joints in composite laminates, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **33**, 1999, pp. 2248-2280.
- [11] G. Liu and K.L. Tang, Study on stress concentration in notched cross-ply laminates under tensile loading, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 2015 (doi: [10.1177/0021998315573802](https://doi.org/10.1177/0021998315573802)).
- [12] Y.W. Kwon and L.E. Craugh, Progressive failure modelling in notched cross-ply fibrous composites, *Applied Composite Materials*, **8**, 2001, pp. 63-74.
- [13] J.L. Tsai and C.W. Chen, Characterizing tensile strength of notched cross-ply and quasi-isotropic composite laminates, *Journal of the Chinese Institute of Engineers*, **32**, 2009, pp. 327-332.
- [14] E.V. Iarve, D. Mollenhauer and R. Kim, Theoretical and experimental investigation of stress redistribution in open hole composite laminates due to damage accumulation, *Composites: Part A*, **36**, 2005, pp. 163-171.
- [15] S.R. Hallett and M.R. Wisnom, Experimental investigation of progressive damage and the effect of layup in notched tensile tests, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **40**, 2006, pp. 119-141.
- [16] S.R. Hallett and M.R. Wisnom, Numerical investigation of progressive damage and the effect of layup in notched tensile tests, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **40**, 2006, pp. 1229-1245.
- [17] S.R. Hallett, W.G. Jiang, B. Khan and M.R. Wisnom, Modelling the interaction between matrix cracks and delamination damage in scaled quasi-isotropic specimens, *Composite Science and Technology*, **68**, 2008, pp. 80-89.
- [18] S.R. Hallett, B.G. Green, W.G. Jiang, K.H. Cheung and M.R. Wisnom, The open hole tensile tests: a challenge for virtual testing of composites, *International Journal of Fracture*, **158**, 2009, pp. 169-181.
- [19] P.P. Camanho, C.G. Dávila and M.F. de Moura, Numerical simulation of mixed-mode progressive delamination in composite materials, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **37**, 2003, pp. 1415-1438.
- [20] P.P. Camanho, C.G. Dávila and S.T. Pinho, Fracture analysis of composite co-cured structural joints using decohesion elements, *Fatigue and Fracture of Engineering Materials and Structures*, **27**, 2004, pp. 745-757.
- [21] Z. Hashin, Failure criteria for unidirectional fiber composites, *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, **47**, 1980, pp. 58-80.